

Features of Pedagogical Professional Excellence in the Disclosure of Individual Abilities of Students and Full Adaptation to Social Life in a Modern Inclusive Educational Environment

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Abstract:

The article analyzes pedagogical methods applied to the process of inclusive education in general secondary institutions. Also, in the modern environment of inclusive education, the conceptual aspects of pedagogical professional skills and inclusive education are covered in the full adaptation of students to individual abilities, social life.

Keywords: inclusion, pedagogical skill, education, law, method, students with disabilities.

Introduction

One of the main tasks of an educational institution is to create a favorable inclusive environment for the implementation of students with special educational needs in society. An inclusive environment as a pedagogical phenomenon involves organizing the educational process in such a way that all students, regardless of their physical, mental and other characteristics, study together with their healthy peers. This is an important condition for the entry of students with special educational needs into the educational socio-cultural environment, which requires specific psychological and pedagogical support for their socialization and maximum self-realization in society.

We see the main task in studying the conceptual aspects of an inclusive environment as a study of the legislative, regulatory and scientific foundations of inclusive education.

An inclusive environment concerns not only a part of society, but also individuals or groups in need of social protection, since a free democratic society must rely on a fair education system, otherwise

it cannot be long-term and integrated in the future. A fair education system must be based on the principle of inclusiveness.

Main Part

The problems of education of persons with special educational needs are increasingly attracting the attention of scientists and specialists, since education is a sphere of public life responsible for human development. Currently, the possibilities of realizing the right to education of persons with special needs are associated with the existence of a complex of legal, scientific, pedagogical, organizational, methodological and socio-psychological problems.

Scientist V.Lyubarets, the need to include persons with special educational needs in the socio-cultural environment of education, that is, the humanization of society and the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities in education for all, the "social" model of understanding inclusion, social-ma emphasizes the special conditions and inclusion of parents in the educational process as its active subjects.

An inclusive environment includes all participants in the educational process and has advantages for them, in particular:

- for children in need of special education, the opportunity not to be separated from the family, as in boarding schools; social interaction, participation in events, access to local community resources, etc.);
- for children with disabilities - gaining experience in communicating with children in need of special education, understanding versatility, developing moral qualities, etc.;
- for parents of children with special educational needs - the opportunity to participate in choosing and organizing an individual trajectory of the educational process for their child; the opportunity to communicate with the teaching staff and other parents, etc.);
- the opportunity to expand the understanding of inclusive education for parents of other children, the opportunity to support other parents, to contribute to the upbringing of children, their inclusion in an inclusive environment;
- in an inclusive environment of general secondary education institutions, working with children with special educational needs, diversifying their pedagogical arsenal: acquiring new knowledge and skills, abilities, training, qualifications and professional skills;
- economic for the whole society (research shows that the inclusive education system is more economically beneficial than supporting two parallel systems - general and special) and value (development of tolerance, compassion, etc.)

At this stage of development of inclusive education in our country, its implementation is largely ensured for children who need special education associated with life limitations. In addition, practical experience in the implementation of inclusive education in Ukraine shows that there are problematic issues that require more detailed study and solution, in particular:

- biased and stereotypical attitude of society towards individuals with special educational needs;
- insufficient access to inclusive education taking into account the needs and capabilities of children with special needs;
- lack of material, technical and methodological support for the creation of an inclusive environment, special materials and tools for teaching children with special educational needs;
- insufficient specialized training of teachers and assistants to work with children with special educational needs;

- lack of a comprehensive approach to identifying the needs of a child with special needs and providing him and his family with appropriate support based on an interdisciplinary approach.

Inclusion is therefore a process in which issues of diversity should be seen as an incentive to find better ways of living together, accepting visible differences in a positive light and motivating children and adults to learn.

Inclusion aims to identify and remove barriers. It involves collecting, summarizing and evaluating data from many different sources to improve educational policy and practice, and to encourage the learning of children and adults with special educational needs.

Inclusion creates conditions for the participation, engagement and success of all students. The term "inclusion" refers to the availability of a specific learning space for children and how regularly and on time they are attended. The term "engagement" describes the quality of their learning and therefore requires taking into account the views of students. Today, scientists offer various innovative approaches to teaching children with special needs. Regardless of social status, religious affiliation, an inclusive environment provides an individual approach to meeting the needs and rights of each child in education according to their level of development.

Inclusive education of a general secondary educational institution promotes the comprehensive development of students' potential, teaches students to understand and respect human individuality. In this inclusive environment, the main focus is on students' academic performance, where individual needs are respected and met, where both healthy students and students with special educational needs can study effectively.

Modern inclusive education should organize all the work of students with special needs in such a way as to create maximum conditions for the manifestation of their individual abilities and inclinations, for their comprehensive development. Individualization of education, which is expressed in its differentiation, greatly helps in solving this problem.

A teaching staff member can successfully implement differentiated teaching of students with special needs under the following conditions:

- can foresee possible difficulties in the process of studying educational material for children with special educational needs;
- the general readiness of disabled students for the next activity is taken into account, that is, the level of knowledge acquired, the ability to work independently, attitude to work and desires;
- systematically and purposefully uses differentiated individual and group training;
- conducts prospective analysis.

Training competent teachers of inclusive education is one of the conditions for the implementation of inclusiveness. At the moment, the solution to this issue requires both organizational and methodological support. At the initial stages of the implementation of inclusion, teachers encountered obstacles in adapting and organizing an inclusive form of education: uncertainty in the face of the unknown, professional training, unwillingness to change, psychological negativity towards working with people with special educational needs.

To assess the quality of the inclusive process in the education system, it is necessary to develop a set of programs for monitoring the dynamics of the development of the inclusive process, one of such indicators is the readiness of teachers for professional activity.

Social readiness for professional activity in an inclusive environment:

- ability to work with social models;
- the presence of ideological connections;

- the ability to create social relations.

Psychological preparation is manifested in:

- emotional acceptance of children with special educational needs of different types of development;
- readiness to join the educational process in an inclusive environment;
- knowledge of individual characteristics, special educational needs;
- satisfaction with professional activity.

Structure of professional training:

- readiness for information;
- professional competence (cross-cutting, professional, special);
- acquisition of pedagogical technologies;
- knowledge of psychology and correctional pedagogy;
- readiness of teaching staff to model and use variability in the educational process;
- readiness for professional interaction with a differentiated approach to students with special educational needs.

An inclusive environment requires a creative choice of forms, methods and means of organizing the educational process with students in need of special education. Therefore, the teaching staff must have methodological skills that allow them to carry out inclusive activities.

To sum up the above, a mandatory and important aspect is the formation of methodological competence of teachers in an inclusive educational environment, which is possible in the context of improving the quality of their professional competence. One of the tasks is to develop programs for the training and retraining of teaching staff, in particular, in general education institutions, within the framework of the National Strategy for Reforming the System of Education and Upbringing of Children in Institutions and the program of measures for its implementation in 2017-2026. Secondary educational institutions providing education for students with special educational needs; development of criteria for monitoring the process of reforming the system of institutional upbringing, education and upbringing of children with special educational needs.

Conclusion

An analysis of scientific publications containing issues related to the theory and practice of inclusive education workers, as well as a study of the content of educational and methodological materials for professional retraining and advanced training courses, revealed a number of problems. Training of teaching staff of general educational institutions:

- insufficient attention is paid to the formation of a personal attitude towards inclusion and the social significance of its organization among teaching staff of general secondary educational institutions;
- lack of correlation between the goals, content and technology of training teachers to implement the ideas of inclusive education in accordance with the real conditions in which they work;
- lack of interpersonal, theoretical and practical components in the content of education aimed at developing the abilities of teachers of secondary educational institutions to solve professionally important, socially defined problems;

- lack of flexibility and mobility in the organization of the educational process in an inclusive environment, which is hampered by the inability of teaching staff to adapt to the diverse structure of offenses among children in need of special education;
- in the event of professional difficulties associated with the organization of joint training of teaching staff of general secondary educational institutions, identification of special educational needs of children, correction and construction of the educational process, organization of mutual cooperation - lack of methodological support; cooperation with all subjects of education.

It is urgently necessary to develop a strategy for the formation of methodological competence of professors and teachers of general educational institutions in an inclusive environment. From this point of view, in an inclusive environment, training and retraining courses of general educational institutions make a special contribution to the formation of methodological competence of teaching staff.

Taking into account the above, we can conclude that it is necessary to introduce the principles of systematicity, scientific nature, education and research, integrity of the educational process, innovation, professional mobility, individualization, creativity, cooperation, continuity into the professional training of specialists. teachers. This process allows: to determine the current tasks and problems of scientific research in professional activity; determination of the prospects of professional activity, methods and conditions for its implementation; analysis of pedagogical tasks, determination of their structure and justification of the task.

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